

Stigmochelys pardalis Leopard tortoise

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Reptile

Size: Adults usually measure 30 - 45 cm, but in populations at the extremes of their distribution, they often attain 60 - 75 cm.

Distribution:

The leopard tortoise ranges widely across eastern and southern Africa, from Ethiopia and Kenya southward through Tanzania, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Botswana, Namibia, Eswatini, and South Africa. It inhabits savanna, grassland, and semi-arid scrub habitats, preferring loose soil for burrowing.

Importance:

The leopard tortoise is a keystone species in South African savannas, grazing, dispersing seeds, and shaping microhabitats. Genome sequencing can reveal resilience traits, population connectivity, and guide conservation strategies to safeguard the species and maintain ecosystem stability under climate change.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 66.19 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 9.32 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 2.46 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 100.0% [Single: 97.3%, Duplicated: 2.7%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 5 360.99 kilobases

Contig number: 2 219

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr Zhongning Zhao

University of Free State

orochi19851020@yahoo.com

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